

Australian Structural Biology Deep-Learning Infrastructure Roadmap

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Executive Summary

Enabled by advances in deep learning methods for protein structure prediction and de novo protein design, computational structural biology has rapidly emerged as a powerful technology driving innovation in both fundamental and translational science. The technology underpins breakthroughs in drug design, diagnostics, personalised medicine, and synthetic biology. However, effective use requires concentrated interdisciplinary expertise and access to modern graphics processing unit (GPU) hardware that few Australian researchers or industry can sustain.

The Australian structural biology community has taken a collaborative approach to develop this infrastructure roadmap which describes the existing national landscape, identifies and prioritizes critical research bottlenecks, and proposes a national strategy to unlock the immense potential of computational structural biology for Australian researchers. This strategy is intended to evolve as the requirements of the community change. The roadmap outlines the challenges faced but also presents opportunities to maximize the value of this new technology. A robust, sovereign capability in computational structural biology and protein design will position Australian universities, research institutes, and industry at the forefront of global innovation.

The community roadmap outlines 4 major deliverables including:

D1. A dedicated community space to foster collaboration and share best-practice recommendations for software deployments, benchmarking, validations and insights developed within the community.

D2. Community training resources to on-board diverse stakeholders within the context of computational structural biology and strengthen the national impact of community expertise.

D3. National computational infrastructure built on increased hardware investment and a user platform to facilitate efficient, high-throughput utilization of national computing resources and drive translational outcomes enabled by curated and validated computational structural biology technologies.

D4. Alignment, integration and engagement with global best-practice efforts for computational structural biology infrastructure and research.

Achieving these outcomes will not only enable the community to add value across diverse research disciplines within Australia, but will drive innovation and enhance the national research and enterprise profile in medicine and biotechnology on the global stage.

1. Background and Context

Structural Biology is a multidisciplinary field with a focus on the atomic structures of biological macromolecules (proteins and nucleic acids) alone and in complex with small(er) chemical entities. The field encompasses molecular biology, biochemistry, biophysics, protein design and engineering, physical chemistry, computational structural biology, pharmacology and medicinal chemistry, synthetic biology, structural genomics, and systems biology. For the purposes of this roadmap, we adopt a definition of structural biology that includes protein design and engineering, synthetic biology, and computational drug-docking analyses alongside structure determination. A detailed understanding of molecular interactions facilitates a wide range of translational applications across these disciplines, from the treatment of disease (e.g. COVID-19¹) to the development of new biomaterials². Traditionally, the field has been dominated by three main experimental methods: macromolecular X-ray crystallography³, nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy⁴ and single particle cryo-electron microscopy (cryoEM)⁵. More recently cryoEM tomography is also making a significant impact⁶. All these methods rely heavily on extensive human and computational resources⁷.

In 2021, DeepMind (a subsidiary of Google) achieved a groundbreaking milestone with AlphaFold2⁸ — an exceptional artificial intelligence (AI) program that started a revolution in structural biology. AlphaFold2 was trained on a comprehensive dataset of accumulated experimental structures from the Protein Data Bank (PDB)⁹ and was able, for the first time, to predict protein structures approaching the accuracy of experimental methods. This revolutionary technology has also created a feedback loop whereby model predictions enable enhanced experimental determinations via methods such as molecular replacement¹⁰ and modern integrative techniques (e.g. cross-linking mass spectrometry)¹¹ which promise to rapidly expand the scale of experimental datasets. Since the release of AlphaFold2, a new wave of deep learning models have been developed to encompass the entire spectrum of structural biology, ranging from protein engineering¹² to drug docking¹³. In particular, deep learning-based *de novo* protein design was recognised (along with protein structure prediction) as a core innovation in the award of the 2024 Nobel Prize in Chemistry.

¹ Barrantes, F.J. (2021). The Contribution of Biophysics and Structural Biology to Current Advances in COVID-19. *Annual Review in Biophysics*. 50:493-523. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-biophys-102620-080956>

² Zhang, X., Fussenegger, M. (2024) Structural materials meet synthetic biology in biomedical applications. *Materials Today*. 72: 163-182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mattod.2023.12.008>.

³ Rupp, B. (2013). Macromolecular Crystallography: Overview. In: Roberts, G.C.K. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Biophysics*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-16712-6_655

⁴ Roberts, G.C.K. (2013). Protein NMR – Introduction. In: Roberts, G.C.K. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Biophysics*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-16712-6_303

⁵ Nogales, E., Mahamid, J. (2024). Bridging structural and cell biology with cryo-electron microscopy. *Nature*. 628, 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07198-2>

⁶ Baumeister W. (2022) Cryo-electron tomography: A long journey to the inner space of cells, *Cell* 185 (15): 2649-2652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2022.06.034>

⁷ Carugo, O., Djinić-Carugo K. (2023). Structural biology: A golden era. *PLoS Biol.* Jun 29;21(6):e3002187. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3002187>

⁸ Jumper, J., Evans, R. *et al.* (2021). Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold. *Nature*. 596, 583–589. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03819-2>

⁹ Protein Data Bank (PDB) <https://www.rcsb.org/>

¹⁰ McCoy, A., Sammito, M., Read, R. (2022). Implications of AlphaFold2 for crystallographic phasing by molecular replacement. *Acta Crystallogr D Struct Biol.*, 78:1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2059798321012122>

¹¹ Stahl, K. *et al.* (2023). Protein structure prediction with in-cell photo-crosslinking mass spectrometry and deep learning. *Nature Biotechnology*. 41:1810-1819. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-023-01704-z>

¹² Dauparas, J. *et al.* (2022). Robust deep learning-based protein design using ProteinMPNN. *Science*. 378, 49-56. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.add2187>

¹³ Pandey, M. *et al.* (2022). The transformational role of GPU computing and deep learning in drug discovery. *Nat Mach Intell.* 4, 211–221. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-022-00463-x>

As a result of these revolutionary technologies, tasks that once involved years of effort in the lab and cost on average hundreds of thousands of dollars¹⁴ are now being modelled *in silico* at a similar level of accuracy within minutes. Increasing the accessibility of protein structure data has expanded the use of structural biology across the life sciences as computational predictions provide a concrete motivation for detailed experimental structure determinations. It is now commonplace for both structural and non-structural biologists to commence a project with an *in silico* structural model. Evidence of this impact can be observed in the presentation of deep learning models in a large proportion of biochemistry and molecular biology talks at conferences, outside of the structural biology discipline. These advancements expedite discoveries in diverse biological fields, and have great potential to unlock novel realms of understanding and innovation.

However, this new technology comes with several caveats. From an infrastructure perspective, executing code for non-trivial applications requires substantial computational resources not easily accessible to the average biologist. Additionally, the deluge of deep learning-based methods is overwhelming for non-specialists. Critical evaluation of deep learning models requires careful benchmarking which is notoriously challenging since real-world, biologically relevant systems often do not closely resemble available training data¹⁵. While *in silico* predictions can provide convenient outputs, misinterpretation of model predictions can create a significant burden in wasted productivity. To combat these limitations there is a critical need for dedicated infrastructure and transdisciplinary knowledge in computational structural biology to produce, interpret and validate computational predictions at high throughput.

Within Australia, there is currently no national plan to support the required combinations of expertise in computing (i.e. authoring and implementing deep learning code), structural biology (i.e. structure analysis and validation) and computational infrastructure (i.e. appropriate and sufficient hardware) that are the drivers of these recent computational advances. This means that research in this space is often conducted in isolation, taking advantage of limited, localised expertise to address the inherent challenges of the methods. As a result, Australian researchers are missing out on opportunities to share outcomes and expertise, collaborate on projects, and collectively improve infrastructure available at the national level. Developing a national approach not only increases the impact of scientific output but also unlocks economies of scale.

In response to these challenges, Australian research leaders in structural biology have collaborated with Australian BioCommons and its infrastructure partners to create this roadmap. This document describes the problem space for computational structural biology, in both a local and global context, and outlines the creation of an Australian Structural Biology Computing Community initiative to identify infrastructure gaps that, if resolved, will allow the community to identify, curate, and widen access to valuable computational structural biology code—in particular deep learning. The intention of the deliverables described in this roadmap is to expedite the availability and accessibility of structural biology approaches to researchers nationwide, putting best practice in the hands of life scientists and clinicians, adapting the strategy and deliverables as the field evolves, and ensuring that researchers in Australia can match the pace of international competitors.

¹⁴ Hogg, T., Hilgenfeld, R. (2007). Protein Crystallography in Drug Discovery. *Comprehensive Medicinal Chemistry II*. 875–900. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B0-08-045044-X/00111-5>.

¹⁵ Jain, A., Cleves, A.E., and Walters W.P. (2024). Deep-Learning Based Docking Methods: Fair Comparisons to Conventional Docking Workflows. *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2412.02889>

2. Computational methods in structural biology

2.1 What computational methods are used in structural biology?

Prior to the deep learning revolution of 2021, large amounts of experimental data were required for X-ray crystallography and single particle cryoEM. These large datasets produce significant computational challenges relating to handling, movement, processing and storage and have been focal points for the structural biology community within Australia^{16,17}, and globally, for many years.

As with other domains in the life sciences, the analytical approaches to computational structural biology form part of a complex and rapidly evolving ecosystem, the elements of which are at various stages of technological maturity. Here, we capture a point-in-time snapshot of representative computational approaches applied to structural biology. While all elements of the pipeline are tightly interconnected, current technologies can broadly be categorised into four related modules (see **Figure 1**).

The primary module pertains directly to macromolecular **structure prediction**. This workflow is initiated by producing a multiple sequence alignment of related proteins derived from existing enormous sequence databases. Deep learning models can be used to identify structural constraints from these multiple sequence alignments. For example, covariation (involving a pair of residues changing in unison across each row of the alignment) provides evidence for a direct contact in the underlying structure. Using neural networks, these implicit constraints can be combined with structural templates (identified by searching large structure databases) to guide the iterative generation and refinement of predicted molecular structures ranging from individual proteins to large complexes. Candidate predictions are evaluated based on empirical 'confidence' scores and conflicts between different predictions can be resolved using third-party quality assessment tools. Poor quality predictions are recycled in the workflow until model outputs meet satisfactory confidence thresholds. As the prediction of protein structure becomes more routine, pipelines are increasingly focussed on diverse molecular types, post-translational modifications and dynamic ensembles. Integrative pipelines that use experimental data as additional structural constraints are also beginning to emerge and these can be used to improve the quality of predictions for dynamic conformational ensembles.

¹⁶ Aragão, D., Aishima, J. *et al.* (2018). MX2: a high-flux undulator microfocus beamline serving both the chemical and macromolecular crystallography communities at the Australian Synchrotron. *Journal of synchrotron radiation*. 25(Pt 3), 885–891. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600577518003120>

¹⁷ Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project <https://doi.org/10.47486/PL101>

Figure 1. Analysis modules / pathways in structural biology: Deep learning workflows are diverse and complex. Module 1 is central to most methods and comprises structural predictions, which require significant processing power. The core output from this module is a predicted protein structure which is fed into modules 2, 3 and 4. Module 2 is fundamental functional characterisation for environmental and evolutionary disciplines; module 3 summarises protein engineering for synthetic biology and biotechnology and module 4 shows workflows into drug discovery and design.

High resolution molecular structures are a critical component of **rational drug discovery** campaigns, providing rich information to guide downstream medicinal chemistry¹⁸. Validated complex structures between a protein and small molecule can be used as a starting point for drug design by informing small changes to the bound ligand to optimise interaction affinity. In the absence of experimental protein-ligand complex data, computational docking methods that identify candidate binders for a target protein involve comprehensive sampling and scoring of predicted complexes between proteins and small-molecule ligands. Deep learning models have recently been developed to accelerate these docking techniques but the computational burden required to screen the vast chemical space of potential drug structures remains immense^{19,20}. Finally, deep learning models for *de novo* design have also been developed to produce synthetic proteins and small molecules to bind a target and disrupt native functions. Representative

¹⁸ Lyu, J., Kapolka, N. *et al.* (2024). AlphaFold2 structures guide prospective ligand discovery. *Science*. 384, eadn6354. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adn6354>

¹⁹ Catacutan, D.B., Alexander, J. *et al.* (2024). Machine learning in preclinical drug discovery. *Nat Chem Biol*. 20, 960–973. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41589-024-01679-1>

²⁰ Durant, G., Boyles, F. *et al.* (2024). The future of machine learning for small-molecule drug discovery will be driven by data. *Nat Comput Sci*. 4, 735–743. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43588-024-00699-0>

methods involve extensive sampling of candidate designs, which are filtered for likely experimental success using *in silico* quality control criteria.

Fundamental **functional characterisation** is also supported by computational structural biology. Classical functional annotation pipelines utilise experimental evidence to assign functional roles to a small set of well-characterised proteins and these labels are propagated to other proteins based on the similarity of their amino-acid sequences. Structure-based comparisons based on Cartesian coordinates and tokenised representations of structure provide a more sensitive measure of functional relationships and are increasingly used to infer the function of uncharacterised proteins. Finally, molecular visualisation suites are used to visually evaluate functional assignments and interpret complementary functional data, including known disease-causing mutations, in a structural context.

Protein engineering involves the modification of natural protein sequences to optimise particular molecular properties such as solubility, expressibility in bacterial cell culture (enabling cheap protein production), enzymatic activity and binding affinity to target proteins (to enhance a therapeutic effect). Biophysical structural models quantify an empirical energy score to predict the impact of amino acid substitutions. Neural networks have also been trained to generate idealised amino acid sequences expected to fold into a desired input structure.

2.2 Why is the ‘new wave’ of deep learning computing important for structural biology?

Careful utilisation of deep learning tools in structural biology is already having a transformative impact on the life science landscape with numerous downstream applications including:

- Massively accelerating small molecule drug discovery by enabling rapid generation of the structures of drug targets and identification of potential small-molecule drugs *in silico*. In 2024, a DeepMind spin-off company, Isomorphic Labs, announced commercial partnerships with Eli Lilly and Novartis to use AlphaFold technology to identify small-molecule drugs for several undisclosed therapeutic targets with upfront investment of USD 45 M and USD 37.5 M as well as performance-based milestone payments of up to USD 1.7 B and USD 1.2 B respectively²¹.
- Engineering protein machines to optimise therapeutic and industrial applications. For example, the Adaptyv Bio competition²² challenged participants to design binders to the Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) – a well characterised cancer target. The highest affinity binder utilised the commercial Cradle platform to optimise the framework regions of Cetuximab (a commercial therapeutic antibody) and achieve a 5x increase in EGFR-binding affinity²³. In addition, AlphaFold2-based partial-structure generation combined with ProteinMPNN sequence optimisation has been used to engineer a luciferase enzyme to recognise synthetic luciferin substrates²⁴.
- The *de novo* generation of “new to nature” proteins to treat disease and as new tools for medicine, research and biotechnology. In 2025, researchers from the University of Washington’s Institute for Protein Design reported *de novo* designed binders to snake venom toxins which

²¹ Isomorphic Labs kicks off 2024 with two pharmaceutical collaborations.

<https://www.isomorphiclabs.com/articles/isomorphic-labs-kicks-off-2024-with-two-pharmaceutical-collaborations>

²² Adaptyv Bio Protein Design Competition <https://design.adaptyvbio.com/>

²³ Protein Design Competition: Has binder design been solved? <https://www.adaptyvbio.com/blog/po104>

²⁴ Yeh, A., Norn, C. *et al.* (2023). *De novo* design of luciferases using deep learning. *Nature*. 614, 774-780. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-05696-3>

showed *in vivo* protection in preclinical studies²⁵. Binders were designed with a fully computational pipeline using RFdiffusion to generate plausible complex structures, ProteinMPNN to produce amino acid sequences compatible with the designed protein backbones, and AlphaFold2 as an *in silico* quality control metric to confirm that the designed sequences were predicted to generate the expected complex structure.

- Significant 'value adding' to the genomics revolution, allowing protein structures to be generated from the genes present in the vast volume of genomic and metagenomic data generated over the past two decades. A partnership between the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) and Google DeepMind enabled the creation of the AlphaFold Protein Structure Database²⁶, which provides open access to protein structure predictions for more than 200 million UniProt entries, including the entire human proteome. Researchers from Meta made a similar resource available by predicting structures for >600M proteins derived from metagenome sequencing projects²⁷.
- Mining large-scale genomic databases to provide fundamental insights into the workings of biological organisms. For example, Yirmiya, E *et al.*²⁸ screened a library of 32M proteins to identify viral genes that were responsible for disrupting host immunity. Using AlphaFold2-multimer, proteins that were predicted to form high-confidence interactions with relevant host immunity proteins were tested to confirm immunity-disrupting function.
- Greatly enhancing the understanding of molecules that underpin disease causing processes. In 2023, DeepMind announced a fine-tuned version of AlphaFold2 called AlphaMissense²⁹, designed to predict the effect of single amino acid mutations in natural protein sequences. Mutations that disrupt protein structure are commonly associated with disease-causing pathologies. A comprehensive atlas of human protein variants has been predicted, with outputs made publicly available to the scientific community.
- Transforming the field of structural biology by providing a computational toolkit to complement and enhance traditional experimental techniques. For example, *in silico* models are widely used to generate biological hypotheses which motivate experimental investigations. Structure predictions inform the design of minimal biological constructs by trimming flexible termini which can disrupt expression and crystallization³⁰. Constructs can be further optimized computationally by identifying mutations which promote solubility and stability for heterologous expression³¹. Finally, structure predictions can be used to solve experimental structures with X-ray diffraction data by molecular replacement³². These enhanced techniques will be important for generating new experimental datasets to support training models for predicting dynamic systems and large complexes which remain a challenge.

²⁵ Vázquez Torres, S., Valle, M.B. *et al.* (2025). De novo designed proteins neutralize lethal snake venom toxins. *Nature*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-08393-x>

²⁶ AlphaFold Protein Structure Database <https://alphafold.ebi.ac.uk/> & Varadi, M., Anyango, S. *et al.* (2022). AlphaFold Protein Structure Database: massively expanding the structural coverage of protein-sequence space with high-accuracy models. *Nucleic Acids Research*. Volume 50, Issue D1, D439–D444. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab1061>

²⁷ ESM Metagenomic Atlas: The first view of the 'dark matter' of the protein universe <https://ai.meta.com/blog/protein-folding-esmfold-metagenomics/>

²⁸ Yirmiya, E., Hobbs, S.J. *et al.* (2025). Structure-guided discovery of viral proteins that inhibit host immunity. *Cell*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2024.12.035>

²⁹ Cheng, J., Novati, G. *et al.* (2023). Accurate proteome-wide missense variant effect prediction with AlphaMissense. *Science* 381,eadg7492. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adg7492>

³⁰ Gräslund, Susanne, *et al.* (2008). The use of systematic N- and C-terminal deletions to promote production and structural studies of recombinant proteins. *Protein expression and purification* 58.2 (2008): 210-221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pep.2007.11.008>

³¹ Sumida, Kiera H., *et al.* (2024). Improving protein expression, stability, and function with ProteinMPNN. *JACS*. 146.3. 2054-2061. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.3c10941>

³² McCoy, A., Sammito, M., Read, R. (2022). Implications of AlphaFold2 for crystallographic phasing by molecular replacement. *Acta Crystallogr D Struct Biol.*, 78:1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2059798321012122>

2.3 What are the challenges facing computational structural biology?

Although computational resources in structural biology have been a central part of the discipline since its inception, the recent revolution of machine learning / deep learning empowered by modern graphics processing unit (GPU) infrastructure has dramatically changed the landscape of computational structural biology, which is now defined by a number of **key characteristics**:

- **Broad potential impact:** Deep learning technology in structural biology impacts a wide range of researchers—from fundamental evolutionary biologists to clinicians at the bedside. From a financial perspective, effective adoption could transform medicine and address global environmental concerns^{33,34}.
- **Growing diversity of applications:** Large numbers of deep learning models are being created for almost all biomolecular problems. Numerous publications demonstrate that careful applied use of this technology can accelerate protein engineering, drug design, personalised medicine, fundamental understanding and bioprocessing, amongst other applications^{35,36,37}.
- **Vast increases in throughput:** Probable structures for proteins and complexes can now be obtained in minutes to hours with a relatively low real financial cost (in the order of tens to hundreds of dollars per calculation in contrast to the months to years and the average cost of hundreds of thousands of dollars per structure determined experimentally³⁸).
- **Large reliance on predictive modelling and the need for experimental validation:** Current AI methods are a tool, not a substitute, for experimental validation. Contrary to traditional software pipelines, predictive modelling has fewer inherent validation checkpoints to maintain output quality.
- **Rapid evolution of methods:** The field of deep learning is moving very fast, which renders older methods obsolete very quickly. Researchers are faced with the option to continue using older approaches that are slower, less accurate and more expensive, or to rapidly adopt bleeding edge methods.
- **Primarily academic codebases:** Application codebases are contributed primarily by academic scientists and, as a result, projects have limited documentation and ongoing support. Academic incentives are weighted towards releasing new applications rather than long-term project maintenance.
- **Large reference databases:** Existing models require on-demand access to large, dynamic reference databases to provide critical model context and enable high quality predictions.
- **Mixture of commercial, open, custom and unlicensed codebases:** The software licence environment is highly heterogeneous across computational structural biology codebases.

³³ Borkakoti, N. and Thornton J.M. (2023). AlphaFold2 protein structure prediction: Implications for drug discovery. *Current opinion in structural biology*. 78: 102526. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbi.2022.102526>

³⁴ Thornton, J.M., Laskowski, R.A., and Borkakoti, N. (2021). AlphaFold heralds a data-driven revolution in biology and medicine. *Nat Med*. 27, 1666–1669. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-021-01533-0>

³⁵ Kovalevskiy, O., Mateos-Garcia, J., and Tunyasuvunakool, K. (2024) AlphaFold two years on: Validation and impact. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 121.34: e2315002121. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2315002121>

³⁶ Khakzad, H., Igashov, I. *et al.* (2023). A new age in protein design empowered by deep learning. *Cell Systems*. 14.11: 925-939. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cels.2023.10.006>

³⁷ Notin, P., Rollins, N. *et al.* (2024). Machine learning for functional protein design. *Nat Biotechnol*. 42, 216–228. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-024-02127-0>

³⁸ Hogg, T., Hilgenfeld, R. (2007). Protein Crystallography in Drug Discovery. *Comprehensive Medicinal Chemistry II*. 875–900. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B0-08-045044-X/00111-5>.

Interdependent workflows have conflicting licence terms, such as open source projects with commercial dependencies.

- **Handling clinical biomedical data:** The nature of biomedical research often involves the use of real clinical data. This can include structural modelling of patient-specific protein variants or predicting the structural consequences of known disease-causing mutations. Restrictions on this data may make access mechanisms difficult to navigate for researchers.

These characteristics manifest a number of challenges which must be overcome to maximise the downstream value of the recent revolution in computational structural biology.

Software challenges

- **Limited access to deployed software:** Many deep learning packages require specialised computing hardware and have both complex installation processes and multiple complex dependencies. Deploying these tools in production can be a major obstacle for researchers without a strong computational background or access to sufficient institutional computational resources.
- **Critical evaluation of methods:** Emerging algorithms in broad application domains produce a spectrum of results—some are highly accurate, while others have the potential to mislead. This distinction is often not obvious to the end-user. Retrospective benchmarking can artificially inflate apparent performance by evaluating methods on unrealistic test cases that closely resemble training data. Critical evaluation requires careful benchmarking from domain experts, which creates a significant resource burden beyond the capabilities of individual users.

Infrastructure challenges

The computational intensity of deep learning, combined with the anticipated throughput and scale, make access to computing resources a major concern for structural biology.

- **Requirement for computing:** Deep learning is computationally intensive, with a particular requirement for GPUs³⁹. Even small inference workloads are relatively costly compared to other domains such as prompting large language models (LLMs). Additionally, brute force repeated execution of prediction pipelines has been found to dramatically improve prediction accuracy—particularly for challenging protein targets with therapeutic relevance (e.g. antibody-antigen interactions⁴⁰). GPU resources are already under high load due to public demand for LLMs driven by the rise of chat servers like ChatGPT.
- **Heterogeneous computational workloads:** Computational workloads are bottlenecked by disk speed, CPU resources and GPU resources at different stages of structural biology workflows. As a result, workflow deployments require careful optimisation to ensure efficient utilisation of computational resources.
- **Need for interactivity:** The "shape" of GPU provided by High Performance Computers (HPC)s (i.e. batch processing, send your work off and wait for the results) often does not match the shape of work in the context of structural biology (e.g. the need to visualise structures and directly interact with data). Oftentimes, computational structural biologists need to visualise structures and work interactively in their compute sessions. Not all HPC resources are set up to allow this

³⁹ Pandey, M., Fernandez, M. *et al.* (2022). The transformational role of GPU computing and deep learning in drug discovery. *Nat Mach Intell.* 4: 211–221. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-022-00463-x>

⁴⁰ Abramson, J., Adler, J. *et al.* (2024). Accurate structure prediction of biomolecular interactions with AlphaFold 3. *Nature.* 630, 493-500. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07487-w>

relatively new way of working, and effort is required to adapt resources to fit this important growing use-case.

Data-related challenges

As with other biological data, deep learning applications for structural biology raise several data-related considerations including security, privacy, intellectual property (IP), ethics and potential misuse.

- **Data management:** Deep learning methods require and generate vast amounts of data. This includes the number of output files per inference, and also data size when predictions are run in batches. Efficient curation, storage, and retrieval of these datasets demands scalable storage solutions, standardised formats, and thorough metadata annotation. Managing terabytes of reference data collectively is essential to prevent duplication across user allocations on HPC infrastructure.
- **Ethics and data privacy:** Clinical patient data must be rigorously de-identified to protect privacy while still enabling meaningful analysis. While anonymisation is manageable at a smaller scale, the growing demand for high-throughput analyses increases the likelihood of re-identification, thus requiring stronger privacy protections and more rigorous security measures.
- **IP and legal considerations:** It is crucial to clearly define the ownership and rights associated with both the input and output data. For example, some tools may permit academic use while restricting industrial applications. Additionally, bespoke software licence agreements can introduce uncertainty for academic researchers, who may be concerned that compliance with academic licences could inadvertently limit future commercialisation opportunities.
- **Misuse of technology:** There is a non-zero risk that the technology may be misused with malicious intent. Potential examples include using structural biology tools for designing unethical genetic modifications or using the technology to aid development of biological weapons.

The underlying researcher training challenge

Similar to other bioinformatics methods, there is a training challenge that relates directly to the rapid evolution of methods, the opacity of models, and the diversity of users looking to apply deep learning for structural biology.

- **Dynamic materials:** The rapid evolution of methods and increasing diversity of applications requires dynamic training materials to stay up-to-date with the latest advancements and provide best-practice recommendations to downstream users.
- **Opaque outputs:** Deep learning models, particularly neural networks, are not transparent and are often described as 'black boxes'. This lack of transparency makes it challenging to understand how a model arrived at its conclusions. There is a need to support the research community to critically evaluate AI models by providing expert benchmark evaluations which highlight the strengths and limitations of model outputs, and training materials to interpret generated output files. These materials will help users better understand and use software tools and workflows for structural biology.
- **Historical limitations for general structural biology training:** Due to difficulties associated with collecting experimental structure data, general undergraduate courses have historically provided limited training for handling and analyzing structures compared with genomic or protein sequences. The success of AlphaFold2 has brought structure data to the mainstream and motivated the development of additional undergraduate teaching materials to improve literacy in

this domain. The structural biology community has the opportunity to guide the development of these training materials to ensure that they are fit for purpose.

- **Diverse user base:** Researchers from diverse biological disciplines will be accessing and using structural data predicted using deep learning techniques. There is an onus on the structural biology community to provide educational material to help scientists without fluency in structural biology to understand the limitations of, and interpret output from, the large number of deep learning codes available. Training materials need to be accessible to an audience with a range of experience in structural biology and deep learning^{41,42}.

2.4 What is the international community doing in computational structural biology?

The importance of computational resources for structural biology has been widely recognised internationally. The USA's National Institute of Health (NIH)⁴³ built the first biomedical research supercomputer 'Biowulf' in 1999, placing it within the 100 most powerful computers in the world at the time. It has since been acknowledged in over 5000 research papers⁴⁴. In 2014, as a part of a focused plan to drive scientific advancement, the NIH launched a 5 year upgrade initiative to specifically meet the growing needs and capabilities of structural biology⁴⁵. The NIH also funds the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI)⁴⁶ and hosts central databases used by structural biologists and biomedical scientists globally⁴⁷.

Recently, the focus has shifted to AI capabilities via HPC with GPU acceleration. In the USA, a series of Town Halls were delivered in 2019 and resulted in a collaborative report titled "AI for Science" that described a roadmap for AI in the coming decade⁴⁸. The town halls were hosted by members of Argonne National Laboratory⁴⁹, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL)⁵⁰ and Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory⁵¹ and were attended by over 1000 scientific leaders. Despite being prepared prior to AlphaFold2 and other machine learning advancements in structural biology, the report specifically highlighted the need for investment into AI for structural biology. In response to these town hall meetings, the USA has invested significantly into AI at national HPC, making the USA well positioned to take advantage of the recent advances in the field. Structural biology use cases for these national systems include an on-going project that is implementing OpenFold on ALCF supercomputers to predict interactions between any two proteins⁵², usage of the ALCF Polaris system to develop APACE: an

⁴¹ Goodsell, D.S., Dutta, S. *et al.* (2021). Molecular storytelling for online structural biology outreach and education. *Structural Dynamics*. 8.2. <https://doi.org/10.1063/4.0000077>

⁴² Procko, K., Beckham, J.T. *et al.* (2020). Building a Community of Practice for the Assessment of Biomolecular Visual Literacy. *The FASEB Journal*. 34: 1-1. <https://doi.org/10.1096/fasebj.2020.34.s1.00466>

⁴³ National Institutes of Health (NIH) <https://www.nih.gov/>

⁴⁴ History of the NIH Biowulf Cluster <https://hpc.nih.gov/about/history.html>

⁴⁵ Biowulf upgrade as part of NIH Intramural Research Program (IRP) <https://irp.nih.gov/our-research/accelerating-science/advancing-computational-and-structural-biology>

⁴⁶ National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

⁴⁷ Search NCBI <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/search/>

⁴⁸ AI for Science https://www.anl.gov/sites/www/files/2023-05/158802_0.pdf

⁴⁹ Argonne National Laboratory (ANL) <https://www.anl.gov/>

⁵⁰ Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) <https://www.ornl.gov/>

⁵¹ Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (LBNL) <https://www.lbl.gov/>

⁵² OpenFold-Powered Machine Learning of Protein-Protein Interactions and Complexes <https://www.alcf.anl.gov/science/projects/openfold-powered-machine-learning-protein-protein-interactions-and-complexes> & Ahdriz, G., Bouatta, N. *et al.* (2024). OpenFold: retraining AlphaFold2 yields new insights into its learning mechanisms and capacity for generalization. *Nat Methods*. 21, 1514–1524. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-024-02272-z>

optimised framework for running AlphaFold2 at scale⁵³, and genome scale protein structure predictions on the Summit system at OLCF⁵⁴.

At the institution level in the US, University of Washington's Institute for Protein Design (IPD) is a pioneer in the computational structural biology space. The institute boasts >500 NVIDIA GPU accelerators which are critically deployed to deliver translational outcomes across applications including the design of small-molecule biosensors, candidate vaccine antigens, synthetic antibodies, antivirals and antitoxins as well as engineering protein nanocages, nanopores and other nanomaterials. Since its inception in 2012, the IPD has produced 10 spinout companies including Icosavax which was acquired by AstraZeneca for USD 1.1 B in 2024. The IPD director, David Baker, was recognised for developing deep learning models for *de novo* protein design with the 2024 Nobel Prize in Chemistry.

Table 1 summarises the GPU capabilities of some example international computational systems available for research as listed publicly at the time of writing. For comparison, current Australian infrastructure is included and highlighted in orange. Table 1 is sorted in order of GPU processing capacity (GPU is optimal for deep learning applications as opposed to CPU) in TFLOPS (trillions of floating-point operations per second) at FP16 (to enable comparison although values are approximate).

Table 1: Example global computing infrastructure ranked by GPU capabilities.
Highlighted rows are Australian systems.

System	# GPUs	GPU model	TFLOPS (FP16)* per GPU	Approx. Equivalent TFLOPS (FP16)	Top500 Rank ⁵⁵	Location
Frontier ⁵⁶	37,632	AMD Instinct MI250X [§]	383	14 413 056	2	Oak Ridge Leadership Computing Facility (USA)
Aurora ^{57,58}	63,744	Intel Data Center GPU Max Series		(no comparison data available)	3	Argonne Leadership Computing Facility (USA)
AI Bridging Cloud Infrastructure (ABCI) ⁵⁹	6,128	NVIDIA H200 SXM5	2000	12 256 000	39	National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST, Japan)
Leonardo ⁶⁰	13,824	NVIDIA A100	312	1 728 000	9	Tecnapolo di Bologna (Italy)
Perlmutter	6,184 1,024	NVIDIA A100 40GB NVIDIA A100 80GB	312 312	901 000	19	National Energy Research Scientific Computing Center (USA)

⁵³ New computing framework streamlines the use of AI and supercomputers for protein structure prediction <https://www.alcf.anl.gov/news/new-computing-framework-streamlines-use-ai-and-supercomputers-protein-structure-prediction> & Park, H., Haas, R., and Huerta, E.A. (2024). APACE: AlphaFold2 and advanced computing as a service for accelerated discovery in biophysics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 121(27), e2311888121. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2311888121>

⁵⁴ Gao, M., Lund-Andersen, P. et al. (2021). High-Performance Deep Learning Toolbox for Genome-Scale Prediction of Protein Structure and Function. *IEEE/ACM Workshop on Machine Learning in High Performance Computing Environments (MLHPC)*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MLHPC54614.2021.00010>

⁵⁵ November 2024 Top 500 list <https://top500.org/lists/top500/>

⁵⁶ Frontier supercomputer <https://www.ornl.gov/news/frontier-supercomputer-debuts-worlds-fastest-breaking-exascale-barrier> & <https://www.olcf.ornl.gov/olcf-resources/compute-systems/frontier/>

⁵⁷ Argonne Leadership Computing Facility (ALCF) <https://www.alcf.anl.gov/>

⁵⁸ Aurora supercomputer <https://www.alcf.anl.gov/aurora>

⁵⁹ AI Bridging Cloud Infrastructure (ABCI) https://abci.ai/en/about_abci/computing_resource.html

⁶⁰ Leonardo HPC System <https://leonardo-supercomputer.cineca.eu/hpc-system/>

System	# GPUs	GPU model	TFLOPS (FP16)* per GPU	Approx. Equivalent TFLOPS (FP16)	Top500 Rank ⁶⁵	Location
Virga ⁶¹	448	NVIDIA H100	2000	896 000	88	CSIRO, ACT
Della ⁶²	336 276 40	NVIDIA H100 NVIDIA A100 80GB NVIDIA A100 40GB	2000 312 312	770 592	N/A	Princeton University (USA)
Polaris ⁶³	2,240	NVIDIA A100 40GB	312	698 880	47	Argonne Leadership Computing Facility (USA)
ASPIRE 2A+ ⁶⁴	320 ⁶⁵	NVIDIA H100	2000	640 000	90	National Supercomputing Centre (NSCC, Singapore)
HKUST ⁶⁶	440	NVIDIA H800	~750	330 000 (estimate for H800)	N/A	Hong Kong University of Science and Technology
Setonix (Tier 1)	768	AMD Instinct MI250X [§]	383	294 144	45	Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre (WA, Australia)
Raven ⁶⁷	768	NVIDIA A100 40GB	312	239 616	135	Max Planck Computing and Data Facility (Germany)
LANTA ⁶⁸	704	NVIDIA A100 40GB	312	219 648	142	NSTDA Supercomputer Center (ThaiSC, Thailand)
Spartan ⁶⁹	124 40	NVIDIA A100 80GB NVIDIA H100	312 2000	118 688	262	University of Melbourne, VIC
Gadi ⁷⁰ (Tier 1)	640 16	NVIDIA V100 NVIDIA DGX A100	125 312	82 112	130	National Computational Infrastructure, NCI, ACT
Bunya ⁷¹	37 18 6	NVIDIA H100 NVIDIA L40 NVIDIA L40S	2000 170 200	78 260	N/A	University of Queensland, QLD
Phoenix	200	NVIDIA A100 SXM	312	62 400	N/A	University of Adelaide, SA
Katana ⁷²	16 20 1 20 32	NVIDIA H200 141GB NVIDIA A100 40GB NVIDIA GH200 NVIDIA L40S NVIDIA V100 32GB	2000 312 1500 200 125	44 774	N/A	University of New South Wales, NSW
Ngarrgu Tindebeek ⁷³	88	NVIDIA A100 80GB	312	27 456	N/A	Swinburne University of Technology, VIC

⁶¹ Virga news article <https://www.commonwealthunion.com/virga-hpc-cluster-designed-for-ai-workloads/>

⁶² Della <https://researchcomputing.princeton.edu/systems/della>

⁶³ Polaris <https://docs.alcf.anl.gov/polaris/hardware-overview/machine-overview/>

⁶⁴ ASPIRE 2A+ <https://www.nscg.sg/aspire-2a-plus/>

⁶⁵ DGX SuperPOD with 40 DGX H100

⁶⁶ HKUST <https://itso.hkust.edu.hk/services/academic-teaching-support/high-performance-computing/superpod/hardware-specs>

⁶⁷ Max Planck Computing and Data Facility Bits and Bytes Bulletin <https://docs.mpcdf.mpg.de/bnb/209.html>

⁶⁸ LANTA <https://thaisc.io/thaisc-resources/lanta>

⁶⁹ Spartan Documentation <https://dashboard.hpc.unimelb.edu.au/gpu/>

⁷⁰ Gadi <https://nci.org.au/our-systems/hpc-systems>

⁷¹ Bunya user guide <https://github.com/UQ-RCC/hpc-docs/blob/main/guides/Bunya-User-Guide.md>

⁷² About Katana https://docs.restech.unsw.edu.au/using_katana/about_katana/#gpu-compute

⁷³ Ngarrgu Tindebeek <https://supercomputing.swin.edu.au/ngarrgu-tindebeek>

System	# GPUs	GPU model	TFLOPS (FP16)* per GPU	Approx. Equivalent TFLOPS (FP16)	Top500 Rank ⁶⁵	Location
M3 ⁷⁴	60	NVIDIA V100 16GB	125	17 112	N/A	Monash University, VIC
	12	NVIDIA V100 32GB	125			
	26	NVIDIA A100 80GB	312			
Milton	6	NVIDIA A100 40GB	312	3 412	N/A	Walter and Eliza Hall Institute, VIC
	28	A30 24GB	40			
	20	P100 12GB	21			

* TFLOPs approx. for each GPU card type. Can vary depending on whether TensorCore Sparsity is enabled and other configurations.

§ Note that most Deep Learning code for structural biology does not run natively on this GPU type.

The European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL)⁷⁵ EBI⁷⁶ hosts UniProt⁷⁷, a standard reference repository for protein sequence entries and paired annotations. This is, of course, representative of broader efforts across Europe, with significant computational development in biology being made by EMBL⁷⁸ and the European Union (EU) Horizon 2020 program⁷⁹ which funded, for example, the establishment of the BioExcel Center of Excellence for Computational Biomolecular Research across Sweden, Netherlands, Germany, Spain, Finland and Norway⁸⁰. The EU has also created the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU) to lead the way in European supercomputing, which lists nine supercomputers across Europe⁸¹, with €20 billion committed to five “AI Gigafactories”⁸². Example structural biology projects on EuroHPC JU systems include protein design using a denoising diffusion probabilistic model (DDPM)⁸³, and using AlphaFold2 to guide molecular dynamics simulations and Markov state modelling⁸⁴. The ELIXIR⁸⁵ supported 3D-BioInfo⁸⁶ Community also provides an example of a community driven effort that advocates for the importance of computational methods to structural biology, and supports the formation of community connections, collaborations, standards and policies.

Asia is also responding to the race for improved GPU computational infrastructure. Examples of large infrastructure supercomputer investments include ASPIRE 2A+ in Singapore, LANTA in Thailand, IndiaAI in India⁸⁷, and Neuron⁸⁸ in Seoul at KISTI National Supercomputing Centre. Additional community

⁷⁴ GPU Look-Up Tables <https://docs.massive.org.au/old-M3/M3/GPU-docs/GPU-look-up-tables/>

⁷⁵ European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) <https://www.embl.org/>

⁷⁶ EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI) <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/>

⁷⁷ UniProt <https://www.uniprot.org/>

⁷⁸ EMBL IT infrastructures <https://www.embl.org/about/info/it-services/it-infrastructure/>

⁷⁹ European Union Horizon 2020 program

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-2020_en

⁸⁰ BioExcel Center of Excellence for Computational Biomolecular Research <https://bioexcel.eu/>

⁸¹ European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU)

https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/supercomputers/our-supercomputers_en

⁸² AI Factories <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/ai-factories>

⁸³ Genie 3.0.: an optimized denoising diffusion probabilistic model for protein design

https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/genie-30-optimized-denoising-diffusion-probabilistic-model-protein-design_en

⁸⁴ AlphaFold2-guided Markov state modeling the conformational landscape of inflammasome activation

https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/access-our-supercomputers/awarded-projects/alphafold2-guided-markov-state-modeling-conformational-landscape-inflammasome-activation_en

⁸⁵ ELIXIR <https://elixir-europe.org/>

⁸⁶ 3D-BioInfo Community <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/3d-bioinfo> & Orengo, C., Velankar, S. *et al.* (2020). A community

proposal to integrate structural bioinformatics activities in ELIXIR (3D-BioInfo Community). *F1000Research*. 9(ELIXIR):278

<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.20559.1>

⁸⁷ IndiaAI <https://indiaai.gov.in/about-us>

⁸⁸ Neuron <https://www.ksc.re.kr/byjw/neuron>

initiatives include workshops such as CompBio Asia⁸⁹ and notable cutting edge research from Asian research labs. For example, CASP15 results were best in class from Chinese labs for RNA tertiary structure prediction⁹⁰, for protein-ligand pose prediction⁹¹ and protein complex model accuracy⁹².

3. A Computational Structural Biology community in Australia

3.1 How is computational structural biology being approached in Australia?

The speed at which the field is moving means that Life Science-related Australian Academy of Science Decadal Plans for Science, last conducted in 2016, only address potential roles for AI⁹³, and do not encompass the potential impacts and value of deep learning for structural biology. However, the chemistry plan does specifically mention questions such as “How do proteins fold?”, and “How can we do 3D crystallography in real time?”⁹⁴. The 2021 National Digital Research Infrastructure Strategy (NDRI)⁹⁵ goes further, and specifically addresses the need to make use of “digitally-driven applications”, which includes machine learning—it is worth noting that AlphaFold2 was released after these reports. Aspirations for the Australian NDRI that resonate with the challenges facing computational structural biology include being able to respond when technology shifts, to integrate across different types and scales of infrastructure, and to be supported by foundational elements such as security, training, standards (i.e. access, data collection, data curation), and open access to software. In fact, the deployment of the Australian AlphaFold service⁹⁶, by Australian BioCommons and its infrastructure partners, is included as a case study in being responsive to rapid shifts in technology that can enhance the capacity of Australian research.

Similar to other applications of bioinformatics, computational problems in structural biology have historically been handled locally, and in proximity to the infrastructure where primary data was collected. For example, the Australian Synchrotron⁹⁷ carried the majority of the efforts to handle, transfer and backup X-ray diffraction data (albeit backup responsibility is increasingly being pushed to the user with newer detector technologies and higher throughputs producing ever-increasing dataset sizes). Similarly, the processing of cryoEM data is handled by computing resources located close to the primary data collecting instruments. This is largely due to the sheer size of the datasets and difficulties associated with transferring terabytes of data between locations. Deep learning in structural biology has reversed this dynamic, in that it presents a big *computing* challenge, not necessarily a big *data* challenge. This is exemplified by the model building and inference required for software like AlphaFold2.

Australian responses to structural biology include the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS)⁹⁸, a national effort to link capacity for analysis of microscopy data, including software, services

⁸⁹ Compbio Asia <https://compbioasia.net/>

⁹⁰ Chen K, Zhou Y. *et al.* (2023). RNA tertiary structure modeling with BRIQ potential in CASP15. *Proteins*. 91(12): 1771-1778. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prot.26574>

⁹¹ Shen T, Liu F, Wang Z, *et al.* (2023). zPoseScore model for accurate and robust protein–ligand docking pose scoring in CASP15. *Proteins*. 91(12): 1837-1849. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prot.26573>

⁹² Liu J., Liu D. *et al.* (2023). Estimating protein complex model accuracy based on ultrafast shape recognition and deep learning in CASP15. *Proteins*. 91(12): 1861-1870. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prot.26564>

⁹³ Decadal plans for science <https://www.science.org.au/supporting-science/science-advice-and-policy/decadal-plans-for-science>

⁹⁴ Decadal plan for chemistry (2016-2025)

<https://www.science.org.au/supporting-science/science-policy-and-analysis/decadal-plans-science/decadal-plan-chemistry-2016>

⁹⁵ National Digital Research Infrastructure Strategy

<https://www.education.gov.au/national-research-infrastructure/resources/national-digital-research-infrastructure-strategy>

⁹⁶ Australian AlphaFold Service <https://www.biocommons.org.au/alphafold>

⁹⁷ Australian Synchrotron <https://www.ansto.gov.au/facilities/australian-synchrotron>

⁹⁸ Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) <https://doi.org/10.47486/PL101>

and data repositories. Researchers are able to access convergent resources such as ImagingTools⁹⁹ and the EM Data Processing Portal¹⁰⁰.

With respect to supported research, 25 structural biology projects were awarded by the NHMRC across 2022-2024¹⁰¹. On the computational side, four projects that focused on structural biology were part of the National Computational Merit Allocation Scheme (NCMAS) in 2023 and 2024¹⁰².

3.2 Who is using deep learning computational structural biology in Australia?

Almost all universities and biological research institutes in Australia support researchers that use structural biology in their research in some form, including those whose research is focused on structural biology, and those who use structural data to inform their research programs. Since 2021 and the release of AlphaFold2 there has been an increasing shift towards non-specialist biologists including deep learning modelling in their research papers and deep learning methods are now being used routinely by specialist structural biology researchers¹⁰³. Below, we present anecdotal examples illustrating current applications and impacts of deep learning modelling, contributed by both the authors of this roadmap and select researchers from outside structural biology. As in other fields, the computational segment of the structural biology community remains relatively small. However, their expertise is in high national demand, attracting interest from diverse fields including biology, biodiversity, agriculture, and clinical research.

Example anecdotes from the Australian Community:

Computational structural biologists

- **Dr Thomas Litfin (University of New South Wales):** “My research has focused on developing software infrastructure to process and handle data at the extreme scale now enabled by models like AlphaFold2. Additionally, I have provided consultation about the potential impact and limitations of models for users across diverse biological disciplines to support experimental structure-based functional characterisations.”

Structural biologists

- **Dr Kate Michie (University of New South Wales):** “Of the six papers my group has contributed to in the last year, all contain data output from deep learning structural methods. Of the three published in 2023, two contained deep learning models. All papers in 2022 and prior contained no deep learning models.”
- **Professor Brett Collins (University of Queensland):** “Deep learning methods for protein structure analysis have rapidly become integrated into every project underway in the lab. In 2024, of seven papers published or under review in my lab, all have used these approaches to accelerate discovery and provide fundamental insights into protein function not otherwise possible.”
- **A.Prof. Gavin Knott (Monash University):** “Deep learning computational structural biology is a central technology at the core of the Knott lab’s Snow Medical funded research program. Since

⁹⁹ ImagingTools <https://imagingtools.au/>

¹⁰⁰ EM Data Processing Portal <https://imagingtools.au/em-data-processing-portal>

¹⁰¹ Results of NHMRC grant application rounds <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/funding/data-research/outcomes> & searching for “structural biology” in the Fields of Research (FoR) codes for NHMRC grants across 2022-2024

¹⁰² National Computational Merit Allocation Scheme (NCMAS) <https://my.nci.org.au/mancini/ncmas/2023/outcomes>, <https://my.nci.org.au/mancini/ncmas/2024/outcomes>, <https://pawsey.org.au/2023-allocations/> & <https://pawsey.org.au/2024-allocations/>

¹⁰³ Kovalevskiy, O., Mateos-Garcia, J., and Kathryn Tunyasuvunakool, K. (2024). AlphaFold two years on: Validation and impact. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 121(34), e2315002121. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2315002121>

2022, the lab has leveraged deep learning to accelerate the discovery of novel tools from microbial genomic dark matter and to design biotechnologies.”

- **Dr Debnath Ghosal (University of Melbourne):** “We routinely use deep learning-based tools to segment our tomograms and pick particles from 3D tomographic volumes.”
- **Dr Rhys Grinter (University of Melbourne):** “Deep learning based computational biology is a key tool for the lab, both for protein structure prediction and protein design. We have successfully implemented a range of these methods on diverse research topics.”
- **Dr Matt Doyle (University of Sydney):** “We recently published a project completely born out of a prediction from AlphaFold2¹⁰⁴ that a well characterised protein secretion system found across pathogenic bacteria is not a secretion system at all! AF2 was able to predict molecular interactions and dynamicity even though the detection of these features were not the initial intent of the design of the code. Interdisciplinary use of computational structural biology code is literally overturning established dogma at fast pace.”

Researchers outside structural biology (i.e. life scientists, clinicians, industry)

- **Prof Jake Baum (Head of School of Biomedical Sciences, University of New South Wales):** “Few labs haven’t been impacted directly by the recent strides forwards in deep learning computational structural biology. This rapidly evolving technology is becoming central to so many of the projects we are pursuing in my lab from phylogenetic understanding to structural prediction and entirely computational biologics design. Its power will undoubtedly shape how we, and the infectious disease community more widely, pursue drug and vaccine discovery, design and implementation. It is quite simply transformational.”
- **Dr Emily Oates (Clinical geneticist, University of New South Wales):** “I lead the UNSW Medical Genomics Team. Our goal is to improve genetic neurological disease diagnosis rates, identify and characterize new disease genes and disorders and develop novel treatments. We have used AI to model the protein-level impact of genomic variants of interest identified in individuals with rare neurological diseases who remain without a genetic diagnosis after best practice clinical genetic/genomic testing. We use AI modelling to identify variants that are most likely to be disruptive to protein structure and/or function and therefore worthy of further investigation (‘variant triaging’). In one of our research families, not only did this approach result in us ultimately identifying the correct genetic diagnosis after more than 20 years of testing, it also resulted in the identification of a potential new treatment approach for their affected family member. We are also modelling the RNA-level structural impact of disease-causing variants in the rapidly growing group of RNA-encoding (rather than protein-encoding) human disease genes. This technology is incredibly exciting. We can’t wait to see where it takes us next!”
- **Professor Marc Wilkins (University of New South Wales):** “We have found the new structure prediction tools to be invaluable. In a very large scale study using protein crosslinking and mass spectrometry, we confirmed structural predictions for hundreds of human proteins. The combination of structural models and experimental data gave insights into structure, and confidence in structures, over and above that from just one approach. We have also found structural models to be invaluable for understanding mechanisms of interactions between protein methyltransferase enzymes and their substrates. The capacity of prediction tools to build structural models for two or more proteins that interact is extraordinary and revolutionizes the way we can understand how proteins are post-translationally modified.”

¹⁰⁴ Hanson, S.E., Dowdy, T., *et al.* (2024). The patatin-like protein PlpD forms structurally dynamic homodimers in the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* outer membrane. *Nature Communications* 15(1),4389 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-48756-6>.

3.3 What computational challenges are facing the Australian research community?

As members of the global community, Australian structural biologists share many of the challenges facing international peers. For example, the highly dynamic nature of AI software development in computational structural biology creates significant demand for specialised cross-disciplinary expertise to develop and interpret critical model outputs. International leaders benefit from a tightly coupled feedback loop which iterates between the generation of primary experimental data, computational method development and rapid experimental validation. Meanwhile, Australian expertise is often siloed across disciplines which can limit the pace of potential innovations.

Similarly, the scale of data and computing requirements required to deliver deep learning technology for biological science necessitates significant investment into infrastructure resources to support high-throughput workloads. The two peak Tier 1 computational facilities are Gadi, at the National Computational Infrastructure, NCI¹⁰⁵, and Setonix, at the Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre¹⁰⁶ while Tier 2 facilities are mostly co-located within academic institutions (summarised in Table 1). These computing resources are shared, and primarily serve broad disciplines (mostly physics, astronomy, material science, engineering and climate science¹⁰⁷), while other biological sciences (including genomics, proteomics and imaging) also have an increasing need for computing hardware. As a result, the demand for research throughput in computational structural biology is not currently well serviced.

This resource limitation is exacerbated as national demand for training workloads is also beginning to materialise. Australia is particularly exposed to this challenge since the national GPU infrastructure is extremely limited in the context of the global landscape—specifically with respect to modern NVIDIA hardware, which natively supports deep learning workflows. As an example, training a highly optimised re-implementation of AlphaFold2 has been estimated to require >20,000 A100-hours which is equivalent to >50 days using the entire national A100 capacity at the NCI. During development, numerous training runs are required to optimize relevant settings before finalising a fit for purpose deep learning model. While several deep learning structural biology packages have been adapted for AMD compatibility, there is remaining technical debt for existing and developing packages that must be overcome to enable broad utilization of AMD GPU hardware.

Finally, sensitive commercial and biomedical data requires careful handling to ensure safety and to protect financial interests. Consequently, systems that support clinical workflows and data storage should comply with relevant ISO 27000 standards and adhere to ARC and NHMRC guidelines^{108,109,110}. If users intend to publish new models trained on private data, national informed consent guidelines may need revision to explicitly address risks related to training data leakage¹¹¹.

¹⁰⁵ Gadi <https://nci.org.au/our-systems/hpc-systems>

¹⁰⁶ Setonix <https://pawsey.org.au/systems/setonix/>

¹⁰⁷ National Computational Merit Allocation Scheme 2025 Outcomes <https://my.nci.org.au/mancini/ncmas/2025/outcomes>

¹⁰⁸ Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research, 2018, ISBN 9781864960136,

<https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/publications/australian-code-responsible-conduct-research-2018>

¹⁰⁹ Management of Data and Information in Research: A guide supporting the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research, 2019 ISBN Online: 978-1-86496-033-4

¹¹⁰ Secure eResearch Platform technology hosted at Monash University is supported by ARDC co-investment via the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) doi.org/10.47486/PL058

¹¹¹ Carlini, N., Hayes, J. *et al.* (2023). Extracting Training Data from Diffusion Models. *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2301.13188>

3.4 Is a shared national solution desired by the research community?

There is deep interest within the national structural biology community to develop shared resources, as it is often beyond the skill and funding of individual research groups to establish the pipelines required to install, develop and run the code locally. The structural biology and HPC communities recognize the potential for shared resources configured by experts to bring an economy of scale that ensures the resources are well used. This collaborative philosophy reduces maintenance costs and ensures that the researchers have affordable access to technology that would otherwise be inaccessible.

This community has a long history of sharing resources successfully, including the Australian Synchrotron and CryoEM facilities for single particle reconstruction. User data from the Australian AlphaFold Service showed that as of July 2025¹¹², there were 250 individual users that had used the service, with the top users nationally coming from csiro.au domains names, as well as anu.edu.au for ACT, unsw.edu.au from NSW, uq.edu.au from Queensland, adelaide.edu.au for SA, unimelb.edu.au for Victoria and uwa.edu.au from WA. A total of 19,609 jobs have been run, the average number of jobs was 78 per user, and the top user at the University of Melbourne submitted over 10,000 jobs.

A community initiative provides an important opportunity to bridge cross-disciplinary divides and enable rapid feedback mechanisms between computational method developers and experimental practitioners. Lowering the barriers associated with specialized domain knowledge in these disciplines can rapidly accelerate national scientific developments across both fields. For example, the UNSW Mark Wainwright Analytical Centre's Structural Biology Facility supports researchers to use pilots of various deep learning code for structural biology. It is estimated that 90% of structural biology deep learning code users initially only intend on running several planned experiments, and will develop more complicated experiments when the right enabling support is provided, and as they experience the value of the technology when applied to their real world project.

3.5 A community response to challenges in computational structural biology

In Australia, investments to establish community-scale infrastructure to support bioinformatics-based research have materialised in various forms and scales over the last decade under a range of funding schemes¹¹³. One significant supporter is Bioplatforms Australia¹¹⁴, which aims to develop and support Australia's national bioinformatics infrastructure and is funded under the Federal Government Department of Education's National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS)¹¹⁵.

Since 2019, Bioplatforms Australia has supported Australian BioCommons ("BioCommons"); an initiative focused on enhancing Australian life sciences research by establishing improved access to the requisite bioinformatics tools, methods, datasets, computational infrastructure, that underpin world-class science. BioCommons consults with national communities of practice to gain input from life science researchers, bioinformaticians, and infrastructure providers on their research infrastructure needs. BioCommons then works to identify, configure, connect and support these infrastructures at a national scale to enable world-class life sciences research.

¹¹² The service was launched in April 2022.

¹¹³ Schneider M.V., Griffin, P.C. *et al.* (2019). Establishing a distributed national research infrastructure providing bioinformatics support to life science researchers in Australia. *Briefings in Bioinformatics*. 20:2, Pages 384–389. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbx071>

¹¹⁴ Bioplatforms Australia <https://www.bioplatforms.com/>

¹¹⁵ National Collaborative Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) <https://www.education.gov.au/national-collaborative-research-infrastructure-strategy-ncris>

It is in this context that Australian BioCommons has engaged with the Australian Structural Biology community. BioCommons took the first step to provide broad, fully subsidised, access to structural prediction in 2022, by making AlphaFold2 available within its Galaxy Australia service which provided both an easy-to-use interface and dedicated GPUs¹¹⁶. However, it was not until the 2023 Galaxy Community Conference (GCC)¹¹⁷ that the formation of an Australian community of practice for computational structural biology was identified as an avenue for collectively addressing the challenges presented by deep learning in structural biology. This included the expectation that these challenges, and any associated infrastructure requirements the challenges create, may rapidly evolve in lock step with the increasing diversity of methods being created for the field. BioCommons has supported key research stakeholders to identify and build a national Academic panel of experts (see **Table 2**), establish community purpose and aims, run quarterly community meetings¹¹⁸, establish shared community spaces (e.g. website¹¹⁹, GitHub organisation¹²⁰), facilitate consultations with BioCommons infrastructure partners and the broader computational infrastructure community, and begin a set of pilot activities aimed at fast tracking a national response to the challenges facing computational approaches in structural biology (see implementation section).

This infrastructure roadmap document is a collaborative effort between the new Australian Structural Biology community, Australian BioCommons, and BioCommons infrastructure partners. It is intended to formalise and describe the high level requirements of the community, as related to computational approaches in structural biology and the life sciences, and describe the initial steps being collectively taken to address these challenges. Importantly, this collaborative effort will continue to support the Australian Structural Biology community as new needs arise relating to bioinformatics tools, software, infrastructure or training.

Table 2: Structural Biology Academic Panel *

Name	Affiliation	Role
Dr Kate Michie	University of New South Wales (UNSW)	Node Academic Coordinator, CryoEM, crystallography, Deep Learning
Prof Charlie Bond	University of Western Australia (UWA)	CryoEM and crystallography
Prof Peter Czabotar	Walter and Eliza Hall Institute of Medical Research (WEHI)	CryoEM and crystallography
Dr Emily Furlong	Australian National University (ANU)	CryoEM and crystallography
Dr Debnath Ghosal	Bio21 Institute of Molecular Science and Biotechnology (Bio21)	Cryo-electron tomography, Deep Learning, cryoEM SPA
Dr Rhys Grinter	University of Melbourne	Deep Learning, CryoEM, crystallography
Prof Begona Heras	La Trobe University	CryoEM and crystallography
Prof Thomas Huber	Australian National University (ANU)	Biophysics, Structural Bioinformatics, Deep Learning
Prof Bostjan Kobe	University of Queensland (UQ) - IMB	CryoEM, crystallography, biophysics

¹¹⁶ Launching the Australian AlphaFold Service <https://www.biocommons.org.au/news/alphafold>

¹¹⁷ Galaxy Community Conference (GCC) 2023 <https://galaxyproject.org/events/gcc2023/>

¹¹⁸ Computational structural biology - ROLLING AGENDA

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1miRyOOOW7HeDsCvzJwVEOhaAzPBve8od9WUvsAsFfcw/edit#heading=h.m4vfrqp8q3dx>

¹¹⁹ Australian Structural Biology Computing website <https://australian-structural-biology-computing.github.io/website/>

¹²⁰ Australian Structural Biology Computing GitHub organisation <https://github.com/Australian-Structural-Biology-Computing>

Name	Affiliation	Role
A/Prof Mark Larance	University of Sydney	Proteomics
A/Prof Thomas Ve	Griffith University	CryoEM and crystallography
A/Prof Nadia Zatsepin	Swinburne University of Technology	Serial femtosecond crystallography
Prof Joel Mackay	University of Sydney	NMR
Prof Brett Collins	University of Queensland (UQ) - IMB	CryoEM, crystallography, Deep Learning
Prof Michael Parker	Bio21, The University of Melbourne	CryoEM Crystallography and Drug Discovery
Dr Craig Morton	CSIRO	Crystallography and Deep learning
Dr Gavin Knott	Monash University	Deep learning, Crystallography, CryoEM
Dr Matthew Doyle	University of Sydney	Deep Learning, CryoEM
Dr Fiona Whelan	University of Adelaide	CryoEM, Deep Learning, Crystallography, SAXS

*This group is intended to be inclusive and new members are invited to join and contribute to the panel. It is expected that membership of the panel will vary over time.

3.6 Anticipated impact

Addressing the challenges outlined in this document and securing sovereign computational capability is essential for Australian researchers to maintain global competitiveness and continue performing world-class biomolecular research. Achieving this capability is critical to enabling researchers to confidently and rapidly adopt modern deep learning technologies, which in turn will unlock significant benefits. For example, greater investment in computational infrastructure for Structural Biology will support and accelerate the translation of academic research into industrial and biomedical applications, driving innovation across biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, and precision medicine sectors. This may also stimulate technology transfer, entrepreneurship, the formation of start-ups, attraction of private investment, job creation and economic diversification within Australia's life sciences sector. Structured investment will also deliver sustained long-term efficiencies by leveraging economies of scale. Given the potential environmental impacts of growing computational requirements in AI, the community efforts will reduce replication of effort, share knowledge about the most efficient approaches, and provide a mechanism to work directly with peak infrastructures to minimise environmental impact. Additionally, such infrastructure will bolster national preparedness and resilience, enabling rapid response to health crises, including pandemics and biosecurity threats, through faster vaccine and therapeutic development.

The potential cost to Australia of failing to support and advance this technology extends beyond the loss of international standing, greatly exceeding the typical financial return of 1:3.32 associated with research funding¹²¹. Australia's capacity to attract and retain world-class scientific talent will also be significantly strengthened through access to cutting-edge computational resources and a supportive research environment. By aligning closely with national government priorities—including technology sovereignty, innovation, public health preparedness, and workforce development—this infrastructure initiative will maximise opportunities for policy and financial support.

¹²¹ ACIL Allen. (2023). Impact Assessment of ARC-funded Research. https://www.arc.gov.au/sites/default/files/2023-08/Impact%20assessment%20of%20ARC-funded%20research%20-%20Final%20report_0.pdf

The Australian Structural Biology Computing community is well positioned to leverage enhanced computational infrastructure to facilitate deeper collaboration, knowledge sharing, and exchange of best practices among researchers across disciplines. Improved infrastructure will substantially boost research capability by providing reliable access to curated, high-quality computational codebases and advanced tools specifically optimised for Australia's leading computational resources.

Collaboration between the existing national community, BioCommons, and infrastructure providers will further amplify training and skills development opportunities. These joint efforts will support the collective creation and dissemination of educational resources, directly benefiting students and early-career researchers. Enhanced computational infrastructure can accelerate innovation, enabling the exploration of new, challenging, or previously inaccessible research questions. This will drive increased scientific outputs and targeted research funding initiatives based on clearly articulated community needs. Moreover, structured national infrastructure support will enhance global recognition, enabling Australian researchers to actively engage with—and contribute meaningfully to—cutting-edge international research.

Finally, developing sovereign computational capabilities ensures strong governance over sensitive biomolecular data, providing a pathway to safeguard Australia's research within a secure and ethically robust framework. Commitment to sustainable, environmentally responsible computational infrastructure further positions Australia as a leader in ethical and forward-thinking research practices, underpinning broader societal and environmental sustainability objectives.

4. Community recommendations

4.1 Community objectives

As described above, an Australian Structural Biology Computing community has already been established¹²², including an academic advisory panel (see **Table 2**), that represents a diverse spectrum of the structural biology and biophysics community. This community collaborates with their peers to:

- **Collectively create and maintain community forums and centralised collaboration platforms** to support collaboration and knowledge sharing (i.e. methods, validation and documentation);
- **Foster collaboration** between structural biologists, computer scientists, and data scientists, thereby **creating interdisciplinary teams** to help tackle complex challenges, validate results and ensure robust applications of deep learning methods;
- **Lead the review, prioritisation, testing, optimisation, and sharing of deep learning** codes, software and approaches that are of broad relevance and interest to the Australian research community;
- **Develop quality assessment tools** to help evaluate the quality of calculated structures and *de novo* protein designs, as well as help guide researchers towards reliable predictions;
- **Address the ethical implications** of AI-driven structural predictions, as well as discuss transparency, bias and interpretability to ensure responsible use of these technologies;
- **Collectively create new training materials** for both current and future structural biologists, as well as non-structural biologists and researchers that do not have a background in structural biology, but wish to utilise structural data;

¹²² Australian Structural Biology Computing community <https://australian-structural-biology-computing.github.io/website/>

- **Ensure that fit for purpose training in computational structural biology** is accessible to the community, including the current and next generation of structural biologists; and,
- **Build connections to other communities** with overlapping scope (e.g. structural mass spectrometry and proteomics).

A critical output from these collaborative community efforts will be to share collective recommendations for the use of specific codebases that have value and broad relevance to the Australian life science research community in the fields of structural biology, synthetic biology and biophysics. The community may share evaluations of code functionality, quality, usability, its potential impact on research, and the computational resources required to run the recommended codebases effectively. Both documentation and guidelines may be used as a sharing mechanism, and these digital resources will help researchers to understand and efficiently utilise both the reviewed codebases and the infrastructure required to run them. This is where international engagement and contributing to existing international efforts provide economies of scale.

4.2 Infrastructure objectives

To address the computational challenges outlined, and support the objectives of the community, the Australian Structural Biology Computing community will work with BioCommons, and its infrastructure partners, on several high level infrastructure objectives:

1. **To provide shared online spaces and mechanisms that can** enable the community objectives outlined above, including knowledge sharing, evaluation of software, and collaboration.
2. **To describe and coordinate a training program** that will support the research community to understand and use data, software tools and workflows for structural biology.
3. **To provide all Australian researchers with access to a shared platform, or platforms**, with prioritised and validated tools and workflows that are relevant for deep learning methods in structural biology, supported by sufficient computational resources, connections to data storage appropriate security and straightforward access, and guidance and training to enable researchers to understand and use the platforms.
4. **To address these objectives in the context of international efforts** in structural biology: aligning, adopting, collaborating and contributing where possible.

Figure 2. Overarching infrastructure goal for the Australian Structural Biology Computing community, to provide support for a diverse range of researchers to use HPC for biomolecular research.

4.3 Infrastructure deliverables / outputs

To address the infrastructure objectives, four broad infrastructure components / deliverables are proposed for implementation (see **Figure 3**):

- D1. An Australian Structural Biology Computing **community space** capable of fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing for deep learning in structural biology
- D2. A computational structural biology **training program**, developed in conjunction with the community
- D3. A **shared platform, or platforms**, for computational structural biology
- D4. Alignment, adoption and contribution to **global best-practice** efforts

The community may establish metrics that will help determine if the desired requirements and features of the deliverables have been achieved. This includes deliverables that need to become more granular in response to specific requirements of the community, or any changes to these requirements over time as the field evolves: for example the availability of specific methods, including software, is expected to change rapidly and this may also impact the requirements for any platforms that deploy these methods.

Figure 3. Proposed infrastructure to support Australian structural biology computation: **(D1)** Australian Structural Biology community space. **(D2)** Tailored training program connects the proposed infrastructure to the BioCommons training program and includes community generated guidance material. **(D3)** Shared platform, or platforms, for computational structural biology. Protein sequences, or other relevant sequence data (e.g. nucleotide), as well as code, are inputs into the envisaged hypothetical shared platform for computational structural biology analyses, which provides both command-line interface (CLI) or graphical user interface (GUI)-based access to validated software tools and workflows. This system is underpinned by sufficient and appropriate computational infrastructure. **(D4)** Alignment to international best practice highlights the aim to align, adopt and collaborate with international peer infrastructures to deliver the proposed infrastructure. Arrows indicate the general flow of data. See **Appendix 1** for a list of open source tools / workflows that may be included in D3. Globe image: Ciker-Free-Vector-Images, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons.

D1. An Australian Structural Biology community space capable of fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing for deep learning in structural biology

To address objective 1 (*i.e. to provide shared online spaces and mechanisms that can enable the community objectives*), it is proposed to adopt collaborative platforms that encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing across the structural biology community, and thus accelerate technology adoption and develop expertise nationally. It is proposed to adopt platforms that:

- A. Enable democratic input to the national direction of computational structural biology.
- B. Aid the community to identify new use cases and deep learning code.
- C. Centralise and support collaborations focused on triage, validation, testing, deployment, and sharing of deep learning code.
- D. Deploy web resources that will help foster collaboration between structural biologists, computer scientists, and data scientists and also amongst more general biological and medical scientists.

- E. Connect users nationally to reduce siloing, make the process of adopting new technologies easier, and create an interface between deep learning experts, researchers, and infrastructures.
- F. Direct users to the most up-to-date technologies, including triaged and validated deep learning code.
- G. Support researchers to understand and reuse deep learning code for their use cases by sharing general methods and documentation, including guides for common and critical approaches in computational structural biology.
- H. Develop the quality assessment tools required to help researchers evaluate the quality of calculated structures.
- I. Connect the community to the specific resources and / or services created by the other deliverables (D2-D4).

D2. A computational structural biology training program, developed in conjunction with the community

To address objective 2 (*i.e. to describe and coordinate a training program that will support the research community to understand and use data, software tools and workflows for structural biology*) it is proposed to implement / deploy comprehensive training resources, guides, and documentation for the described deliverables that:

- A. Make it easier for any Australian researcher to gain expertise in structural biology tools, workflows and infrastructure options (described in D1 and D3).
- B. Build educational initiatives that bridge the gap between structural biologists and those wishing to utilise this technology. Workshops, online courses, and mentorships can equip researchers with the skills needed to navigate this new landscape.

D3. A shared platform, or platforms, for computational structural biology

To address objective 3 (*i.e. provide all Australian researchers with access to a selection of prioritised and validated tools and workflows that are relevant for deep learning methods in structural biology*) it is proposed to implement a platform, or platforms, in Australia that:

- A. Includes a targeted set of prioritised computational tools that are optimised and validated for structural biology:
 - a. Prioritised by the community, optimised for the required computational infrastructures, and validated by experts within the community for scientific quality. The metrics for selecting software tools that will be supported by any shared platform, as well as those for validation, should be made available.
 - b. Installed (dependencies included) on suitable command line interface (CLI) analysis environments (tier 1 and 2 HPC, but also both national and commercial cloud) where relevant, and underpinned by appropriate computational resources.
 - c. Installed and optimised on graphical user interface (GUI) cloud based analysis platforms (e.g. Galaxy Australia) where relevant, and underpinned by appropriate computational resources.
- B. Where possible, makes use of software tools and workflows that are also available as findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) builds and/or containers that can support self-deployment on local / institutional or independent computational infrastructures.
- C. Includes a user-friendly and highly accessible structure prediction platform component that enables non-experts in the life sciences, and beyond, to submit sequence data and obtain structure predictions.

- D. Has expert support available to help install, optimise and/or containerise additional software tools and workflows, and policies for sustainable maintenance, updates and version control of these tools/workflows.
- E. Is configured by infrastructure experts, to ensure optimal workflows and return high efficiencies. This style of computing is heavy, with complicated dependencies and large energy expenditures.
- F. Is easily connectable to suitable community data storage locations, including: public databases (e.g. the World Wide Protein Data Bank <http://www wwpdb.org/>, the EMBL EBI AlphaFold Protein Structure Database, and UniProt); various data storage solutions including national, institutional or other data storage options; as well as the ability to upload and incorporate user-generated data.
- G. Has appropriate user authorisation and sharing mechanisms to allow for secure data sharing, solely at the discretion of a data owner/custodian.
- H. Takes into consideration relevant ethics, privacy, and intellectual property related challenges.
- I. Includes user-friendly and community contributed and curated documentation, supported by experts in computational structural biology and computational infrastructure, and addressing aspects of the software tools, workflows and the shared platform.

D4. Alignment, adoption and contribution to global best-practice efforts

To address objective 4 (*i.e. to address these objectives in the context of international efforts in structural biology: aligning, adopting, collaborating and contributing where possible*) it is proposed to:

- A. Support and/or establish, and maintain, forums that allow information exchange and collaboration between the Australian and international structural biology communities.
- B. Where possible, actively participate in, align to, and / or adopt international efforts, and where possible, contribute and integrate Australian efforts.

5. Implementation

It is intended that the components identified in section 4 will be implemented throughout 2025 and in 2026 / 2027. Several key activities that are relevant to the proposed infrastructure are already underway.

Component	Notes / status
<p>D1-A. Enable democratic input to the national direction of computational structural biology</p> <p>D1-E. Connect users nationally to reduce siloing, make the process of adopting new technologies easier, and create an interface between deep learning experts, researchers, and infrastructures</p>	<p>As with other domain specific communities, BioCommons coordinates a quarterly meeting series that enables members of the structural biology community to connect, share knowledge, and collaborate¹²³.</p> <p>This forum is open to all, and the entire community, including BioCommons infrastructure partners and collaborators, is encouraged to attend and contribute to the discussions.</p> <p>Included in this implementation component is the ongoing onboarding of new community members, and building bridges to other communities, both within Australia and internationally (e.g. ELIXIR 3D-BioInfo). Critical to this effort will be the development of contribution guidelines for the community, tailored to the types of contributions being made (e.g. software, training, guides).</p> <p>Synthesising inputs from community meetings, forums, and projects into a meaningful set of infrastructure requirements will be part of the ongoing consultation between the community and the Australian BioCommons.</p>

¹²³ Community meetings <https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/struct-bio-community>

Component	Notes / status
<p>D1-D. Deploy web resources that will foster collaboration between structural biologists, computer scientists, and data scientists and also amongst more general biological and medical scientists</p> <p>D1-I. Connect the community to the specific resources and / or services created by the other deliverables (D2-D4)</p>	<p>BioCommons and the community leads have collaborated to launch a website for the Australian Structural Biology Computing community: https://australian-structural-biology-computing.github.io/website/.</p> <p>The website is built using an ELIXIR Toolkit Theme template that is in broad use by BioCommons¹²⁴, and is hosted via a new GitHub organisation set up specifically for the community¹²⁵.</p> <p>The website, in combination with BioCommons domain page¹²⁶, will help to connect community members to resources or services.</p>
<p>D1-F. Direct users to the most up-to-date technologies, including triaged and validated deep learning code</p>	<p>Multiple services are available which can be used to direct researchers to structural biology tools and workflows, including registries such as bio.tools¹²⁷, BioContainers¹²⁸, and WorkflowHub¹²⁹.</p> <p>The community and BioCommons are exploring a combination of tools and services that can provide a practical pathway for community members to contribute triaged and validated approaches, including recommendations.</p> <p>Connecting D1-G below with this component (D1-F) will help users to identify the most appropriate workflow that contains the most suitable tools for their use case.</p>
<p>D1-G. Support researchers to understand and reuse deep learning code for their use cases by sharing general methods and documentation, including guides for common and critical approaches in computational structural biology</p>	<p>Tailored How-to Guides are being developed by the community to guide researchers in applying methods for computational structural biology and deep learning. These guides are findable via the community website and the BioCommons How-to Hub¹³⁰.</p> <p>The community is also connected to peer infrastructure efforts in Europe, and in particular the EBI and the PDB. Plans for this collaboration include the co-development of training materials and guides for deep learning in structural biology, which may be added to the existing materials offered by the EBI.</p>
<p>D2. A computational structural biology training program, developed in conjunction with the community</p>	<p>Introductory level training has occurred for software containerisation; getting started with command line, Galaxy Australia, bio.tools/EDAM and R along with many more webinar and workshop recordings. You can search the Australian BioCommons Training Materials Zenodo Repository¹³¹ for materials as well as the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel for recordings from many of these events¹³².</p> <p>Recommended training material for computational structural biology including protein design is being collected and displayed as an interactive table on the community website¹³³, and is available as a Learning Library collection as well¹³⁴. The community intends that open source material developed under the guidance of subject matter experts might inform and assist the development of suitable undergraduate teaching programs nationally. This includes a combination of</p>

¹²⁴ ELIXIR Toolkit Theme <https://elixir-belgium.github.io/elixir-toolkit-theme/>

¹²⁵ GitHub organisation <https://github.com/Australian-Structural-Biology-Computing>

¹²⁶ BioCommons Australian Structural Biology Computing Community page <https://www.biocommons.org.au/structural-biology>

¹²⁷ Bio.tools <https://bio.tools/>

¹²⁸ BioContainers <https://biocontainers.pro/>

¹²⁹ WorkflowHub <https://workflowhub.eu/>

¹³⁰ How-to Hub https://australianbiocommons.github.io/how-to-hub/structural_biology

¹³¹ Training Materials Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/australianbiocommons-training/>

¹³² Australian BioCommons YouTube <https://www.youtube.com/c/AustralianBioCommonsChannel>

¹³³ Australian Structural Biology Computing website <https://australian-structural-biology-computing.github.io/website/>

¹³⁴ Structural biology collection https://australianbiocommons.github.io/Learning-Library/structural_biology

Component	Notes / status
	<p>community co-created content, and external existing resources. Further training material can be located through international bioinformatics training repositories such as TeSS¹³⁵ or GOBLET¹³⁶, and the Digital Research Skills Australasia (DReSA)¹³⁷ platform provides a further way of discovering digital research and training resources from a number of informatics training providers in Australasia.</p>
<p>D3-A. A shared platform, or platforms - Includes key prioritised, optimised, and validated software tools and workflows for computational structural biology</p>	<p>A collaborative effort between the Australian Structural Biology Computing community and Australian BioCommons is working to identify priority tools and workflows for the Australian research community. See examples in Appendix 1.</p> <p>A high priority for the community in 2025 is the availability of binder type structural biology code (e.g. RFDiffusion, BindCraft), and the international collaboration for the development of the ProteinFold nextflow workflow¹³⁸.</p> <p>The existing mechanisms available for sharing software tools and workflows include:</p> <p>Software: site-specific solutions like the Australian BioCommons Tools and Workflows (project allocation if89) provide the ability to share software installs, and their required reference databases, across all users of the Gadi supercomputer at NCI¹³⁹. The community supported BioConda¹⁴⁰ and BioContainers platforms are also available as solutions for rapid software deployment, which can be used across national computational systems in Australia, including NCI, Pawsey, Galaxy Australia, and Nectar cloud.</p> <p>Computational workflows of import to the community can be shared by contributing directly to community efforts in the workflow space (i.e. as for the ProteinFold workflow, which is part of the nf-core¹⁴¹ effort), or by making use of registries such as WorkflowHub or Dockstore¹⁴².</p>
<p>D3-Ab / D3-Ac. A shared platform, or platforms - software tools and workflows installed on CLI and GUI environments</p>	<p>Researchers can easily identify which computational structural biology analysis tools (and versions thereof) are currently installed as modules across several national, state and institutional infrastructures, including Pawsey, NCI, QRIScloud/UQ-RCC, and Galaxy Australia, as well as finding links to downloadable software containers for installation anywhere through the searchable interactive webpage the BioCommons ToolFinder¹⁴³. Tool installation request mechanisms on these systems are also highlighted through the ToolFinder.</p> <p>Workflows being developed as part of the BioCommons are registered on WorkflowHub¹⁴⁴, and those tested on Australian computational infrastructures by the BioCommons 'BYOD' Expansion Project and Workflow Commons¹⁴⁵ projects are highlighted in the Australian BioCommons space on WorkflowHub¹⁴⁶.</p> <p>CLI</p>

¹³⁵ TeSS (Training eSupport System) <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

¹³⁶ GOBLET <https://www.myqoblet.org/training-portal/>

¹³⁷ Digital Research Skills Australasia (DReSA) <https://dresa.org.au/>

¹³⁸ ProteinFold <https://nf-co.re/proteinfold/>

¹³⁹ Shared repository of tools and software (project if89 on NCI) <https://australianbiocommons.github.io/ables/if89/>

¹⁴⁰ BioConda <https://bioconda.github.io/>

¹⁴¹ nf-core <https://nf-co.re/>

¹⁴² Dockstore <https://dockstore.org/>

¹⁴³ ToolFinder <https://australianbiocommons.github.io/toolfinder/> & <https://australianbiocommons.github.io/toolfinder/?topic=structural>

¹⁴⁴ WorkflowHub <https://workflowhub.eu/>

¹⁴⁵ Workflow Commons <https://www.biocommons.org.au/workflow-commons>

¹⁴⁶ Australian BioCommons space on WorkflowHub <https://workflowhub.eu/programmes/8/workflows>

Component	Notes / status
	<p>Deploying and executing Nextflow workflows is possible via the Australian Nextflow Seqera Service¹⁴⁷, which provides a browser based interface for loading, configuring, and executing computational workflows on a selection of pre-configured back end systems such as national and institutional HPC, as well as commercial cloud. Structural biology codes are being actively ported to AMD GPUs (e.g. AlphaFold2, ColabFold, RFDiffusion, ProteinMPNN, OpenFold, ESMFold, Boltz on AMD GPUs¹⁴⁸).</p> <p>GUI</p> <p>As of February 2025, AlphaFold2 is available via Galaxy Australia¹⁴⁹, and Colabfold MSA and Colabfold AlphaFold2 are available from the Galaxy “app store” (i.e. ToolShed)¹⁵⁰, and can be installed upon request.</p> <p>In addition, AlphaFold2 efficiency and usability are being improved with further support from Galaxy Australia, in close consultation with the Australian Structural Biology Computing community.</p>
<p>D3-Ab. A shared platform, or platforms - underpinned by appropriate computational resources</p>	<p>The Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (ABLeS)¹⁵¹ enables increased researcher access to partner HPC systems, and complements existing access mechanisms such as the National Computational Merit Allocation Scheme (NCMAS)¹⁵².</p> <p>ABLeS supports the collaborative generation and sharing of reference datasets of national importance, production bioinformatics approaches at scale, and the acceleration of software deployment to national peak computational facilities.</p>
<p>D3-B. A shared platform, or platforms - FAIR builds and/or containers that can support self-deployment on independent computational infrastructures</p>	<p>The Australian BioCommons works with international peer infrastructures, including ELIXIR (i.e. Research Software Ecosystem¹⁵³, Tools Platform¹⁵⁴), and the Workflows Community Initiative (WCI)¹⁵⁵, to make builds and containers findable, understandable, and deployable, via registries such as bio.tools, BioContainers, and WorkflowHub.</p> <p>The software prioritised, optimised, validated, and deployed by the structural biology community in Australia will be added to this FAIR ecosystem.</p>
<p>D3-C. Includes a user-friendly and highly accessible structure prediction platform component</p> <p>D3-D. Has expert support available to help install, optimise and/or containerise additional software tools and</p>	<p>The community and BioCommons have initiated a Structural Biology Platform project, which aims to collaboratively create an easy-to-use and accessible platform that allows researchers to deploy validated structural biology code on suitable national infrastructure. This may include existing services such as Galaxy Australia, the Australian Nextflow Seqera Service, and ABLeS.</p> <p>This project has started in 2025, and will directly include community members in project management, coordination, implementation, and review. Experts from both the BioCommons BioCloud team¹⁵⁶, and BioCommons infrastructure</p>

¹⁴⁷ Australian Nextflow Seqera Service <https://www.biocommons.org.au/seqera-service>

¹⁴⁸ RSEHPC@ISC24 presentation: AlphaFold x AMD - Uniting Diverse Expertise for Breakthrough Computational Biology https://www.rse-hpc.org/talks/Sarah_Beecroft/

¹⁴⁹ AlphaFold2 on Galaxy Australia <https://site.usegalaxy.org.au/request/access/alphafold>

¹⁵⁰ Colabfold MSA https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/view/iuc/colabfold_msa/6fbd935575ce & Colabfold AlphaFold https://toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/view/iuc/colabfold_alphafold/9d65257c56de

¹⁵¹ The Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (ABLeS) <https://www.biocommons.org.au/ables> & Gustafsson, O. J. R., Al Bkhetan, Z., *et al.* (2023). Enabling national step changes in bioinformatics through ABLeS, the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (3.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10139651>

¹⁵² National Computational Merit Allocation Scheme (NCMAS) <https://my.nci.org.au/mancini/ncmas/2025/>

¹⁵³ Research Software Ecosystem <https://research-software-ecosystem.github.io/>

¹⁵⁴ Tools Platform <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/tools>

¹⁵⁵ Workflows Community Initiative (WCI) <https://workflows.community/>

¹⁵⁶ BioCommons BioCloud team <https://www.biocommons.org.au/team#biocloud>

Component	Notes / status
<p>workflows, and policies for sustainable maintenance, updates and version control of these tools/workflows</p> <p>D3-E. Is configured by infrastructure experts, to ensure optimal workflows and return high efficiencies</p>	<p>partners, will directly assist with the identification, set up, and configuration of platform components. The ProteinFold workflow is one aspect being explored for the creation of a user-friendly interface to protein structure prediction that can operate on peak Australian HPC infrastructures¹⁵⁷.</p> <p>The deployment, support and configuration of additional software, tools, containers and workflows will be addressed through collaboration between the computational structural biologists in the community, the BioCommons, infrastructure partners (i.e. Pawsey, NCI, and Galaxy Australia), and active BioCommons projects including BioCLI¹⁵⁸ and the Workflow Commons. This effort will also connect to the FAIR builds concepts outlined in D3-B above.</p>
<p>D3-I. Includes user-friendly and community contributed and curated documentation</p>	<p>Technical documentation and support is currently being explored in a number of formats beyond the current offerings in the BioCommons: including How-to-Guides, documentation guidelines¹⁵⁹ and through alignment with international registries for tools and workflows (e.g. bio.tools and WorkflowHub).</p> <p>An initial set of How-to Guides have been created by the computational structural biology community, and are shared via their community website as well as the How-to Hub. Creation of these guides, and similar support documentation, by the community will continue and overlaps with both the community space concept (i.e. D1) and engagements internationally (i.e. D4).</p>
<p>D4-A Support and / or establish, and maintain, forums that allow information exchange and collaboration between the Australian and international structural biology communities</p>	<p>Collaborative work has already been initiated with the EU community through the development of the ProteinFold nf-core workflow, and connections to the wider Nextflow community are supported by the BioCommons Nextflow ambassadors¹⁶⁰, planned contributions to further workflow development hackathons, and the BioCommons workflows community¹⁶¹. Community level connections have also been established between Australia, the ELIXIR 3D-BioInfo community, and the PDB/EBI, and in 2025 will involve knowledge sharing, collaborative BioHackathon Europe proposals¹⁶², and the co-creation of new guidance and training material that can supplement and extend the material already available via EBI.</p>

¹⁵⁷ The Australian ProteinFold Service: Interactive prediction and visualisation of protein structure <https://summit.nextflow.io/2024/barcelona/speakers/ziad-al-bkhetan/>

¹⁵⁸ BioCLI <https://www.biocommons.org.au/biocli>

¹⁵⁹ Documentation guidelines https://github.com/AustralianBioCommons/doc_guidelines

¹⁶⁰ Australia's new Nextflow Ambassadors <https://www.biocommons.org.au/news/nextflow-ambassadors?rq=ambassadors>

¹⁶¹ Bioinformatics workflows <https://www.biocommons.org.au/workflows>

¹⁶² BioHackathon Europe <https://biohackathon-europe.org/>

Appendix 1

Representative databases and software tools / workflows that may be included in D3. This list is not intended to be exhaustive, and will evolve over time as new tools, workflows, and databases are created.

Tool / workflow / database / platform	High level description / purpose	URL	Publication DOI
AlphaFold2	Protein structure prediction	https://github.com/google-deepmind/alphafold	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03819-2
AlphaFoldDB	AlphaFold2 predicted protein structure database	https://alphafold.ebi.ac.uk/	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad1011
AFsample2	Protein structure prediction with extreme sampling	https://github.com/iamysk/AFsample2	https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.05.28.596195
AF_unmasked	Protein structure prediction with multimer templates	https://github.com/clami66/AF_unmasked	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-52951-w
AlphaLink	Protein structure prediction with XL-MS constraints	https://github.com/lhatsk/AlphaLink	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-023-01704-z
BindCraft	Protein Binder Design	https://github.com/martinpacesa/BindCraft	https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.09.30.615802
Boltz-1	Open, unrestricted reimplementations of AlphaFold3 methodology for general biomolecular structure prediction	https://github.com/jwohlwend/boltz	https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.11.19.624167
Chai-1	Open, unrestricted reimplementations of AlphaFold3 methodology for general biomolecular structure prediction	https://github.com/chaidiscovery/chai-lab	https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.10.10.615955
ESM Metagenomic Atlas	ESMFold predicted structure database of metagenome proteins	https://esmatlas.com/	https://doi.org/10.1126/science.ade2574
EvoDiff	Sequence-based binder design	https://github.com/microsoft/evodiff	https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.09.11.556673
Foldseek	Protein structure search	https://github.com/steineggerlab/foldseek	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-023-01773-0
Foldtree	Structural phylogenetics	https://github.com/DessimozLab/fold_tree	https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.09.19.558401
FoldMason	Multiple structure alignment	https://github.com/steineggerlab/foldmason	https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.08.01.606130
LigandMPNN	Protein expression engineering	https://github.com/dauparas/LigandMPNN	https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.12.22.573103
MMSeqs2	Protein sequence search	https://github.com/soedinglab/MMseqs2	https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.3988
ProstT5	Protein sequence+structure embedding	https://github.com/mheininger/ProstT5	https://doi.org/10.1093/nargab/qaee150
RFdiffusion	General protein design	https://github.com/RosettaCommons/RFdiffusion	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06415-8
RayGun	Protein minimisation engineering	https://github.com/rohitsinghlab/raygun	https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.08.13.607858

Document Control

VERSION	DATE	AUTHOR(S)	DESCRIPTION
1.0	2024-10-23	Katharine Arwen Michie, Ove Johan Ragnar Gustafsson	Initial version
2.0	2025-03-21	Katharine Arwen Michie, Thomas Litfin, Brett Collins, Peter Czabotar, Matthew Thomas Doyle, Debnath Ghosal, Rhys Grinter, Gavin Knott, Georgina Samaha, Ove Johan Ragnar Gustafsson	Initial community feedback incorporated, content updated, implementation section added
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